

Research Article

A COMPREHENSIVE PROTOCOL OF GENE SEQUENCING FOR BACTERIAL DIVERSITY FOLLOWING ILLUMINA GENE SEQUENCING PROTOCOL: A METAGENOMIC APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Microorganisms are key components of the soil biota. Earthworms are an essential part of the soil fauna in most global soils, represent a significant proportion of the soil biomass and are regarded as a useful indicator of soil health and quality. They maintain the dynamic equilibrium and regulate soil fertility. Very few studies have been done in bacterial population. The purpose of this work is undertaken to study the comprehensive protocol for Illumina Gene Sequencing for bacterial diversity count followed by extraction of DNA from earthworm gut. Two earthworm species were used in this work, *Pheretima posthuma* and *Eisenia fetida* which were named as 1A and 2A respectively. The DNA of the two earthworms gut samples were extracted following c-TAB and Phenol: Chloroform Extraction method. The quantity and quality of the extracted DNA was high and the bacterial count of the extracted DNA gut samples following Illumina Gene sequencing protocol is very productive. This method can be used for other species for bacterial study.

Keywords: Soil biomass, Gene sequencing, *Pheretima posthuma*, *Eisenia fetida*.

INTRODUCTION

Microorganisms are key components of the soil biota (Schimel, 2007). Earthworms are regarded as friends of farmers (Darwin, 1881) due to their role in soil formation and organic matter decomposition. As their activity leads to the formation of physical biostructures such as burrows, castings in soil, they are often termed as "ecological engineers". The genetic makeup of the strains and environment has profound influence on the efficiency of earthworms in bioconversion process.

Microbial ecology studies have provided a better understanding of (Alm *et al.*, 2000) the structure of microbial communities and the evolution of these communities under various climatic, biotic and xenobiotic conditions and (Amann *et al.*, 1995) the activities of microorganisms. For several years, investigations of microbial diversity were mainly based on isolation and laboratory cultivation of bacteria which lead to underestimation of the true diversity.

To better understand the role of earthworms in nature and their potential usage, the mechanisms of earthworm intestinal microorganism and soil ecology (Tamizhazhagan *et al.*, 2016). It is known that earthworms cannot exist on pure microbial cultures but they need mixed cultures of microbial species (Edwards and Bohlen, 1996). It is generally accepted that earthworms do not commonly consume bacteria and actinomycetes but they may proliferate in the process of passage through gut (Kristufek, 1992).

Determining the nature of any links between soil biota diversity and function is a key challenge for current research. A better understanding of the relationship between microbial diversity and soil function requires accurate taxonomic and functional characterization of microbial DNA and RNA extracted from the soil matrix (Nannipieri *et al.*, 2003).

Molecular analysis of 16S rRNA is now central to studies examining the diversity of microorganisms in the

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environment which contains conserved and variable regions that facilitate sequencing and phylogenetic classification. Methodologies for the analyses of a DNA-based phylogeny (using the 16S rRNA gene) are now well established but the direct targeting of 16S rRNA, as a potential indicator of activity (Fleske *et al.*, 1998), has received comparatively less attention, due primarily to the lack of suitable protocols for extraction from natural environments.

Following the complete Illumina workflow 16S metagenomics studies with the MiSeq System can achieve species-level identification of microbial populations efficiently. The workflow includes DNA isolation, library preparation, sequencing delivering an end-to-end solution for 16S metagenomics. By combining the demonstrated Illumina library preparation protocol, the MiSeq System, and simple analysis software, researchers can analyze complex microbial samples quickly and easily.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Collection of earthworm

Two earthworm species *Pheretima posthuma* and *Eisenia fetida* (Lumbricidae, Annelida) were used in this investigation for study of the bacterial diversity residing in the gut of the two earthworms collected from locally available vermicompost. The two earthworm species were named as 1A and 2A for *Pheretima posthuma* and *Eisenia fetida* respectively for further study.

Full grown earthworms were collected and the gut materials were dissected out and DNA extraction process was carried out from both the gut samples. From each earthworm species 20-20 earthworms were selected for DNA extraction procedure. DNA was extracted from gut content of both the earthworm samples by using c-TAB and Phenol: Chloroform Extraction method followed by AMPure XP bead purification.

After extraction of DNA the further process was carried out using Illumina Gene sequencing protocol. The complete procedure is described in the present study. 16S Metagenomic Sequencing Library Preparation Guide is to prepare sequencing libraries targeting the variable V3 and V4 regions of the 16S rRNA gene. Paired-end sequencing was performed on the MiSeq System and data were analyzed using the 16S Metagenomics Application in the BaseSpace analysis environment.

DNA quality and quantity

The absorption spectrum of DNA extracts (230–280 nm and 260–230 nm) was determined using Nano-drop(R) ND-1000 spectrophotometer (Eurofins Genomics Bioinformatics Lab) according to the manufacturer's instructions. DNA was visualized by electrophoresis of 5- μ l aliquots through 1.2% (w v⁻¹) agarose gels containing 0.5 μ g ml⁻¹ ethidium bromide, and DNA was quantified (μ g DNA 0.1 g⁻¹ fresh gut content) as previously described (Thakuria *et al.*, 2008). The QC pass DNA samples were processed for first Amplicon generation followed by NGS

library preparation using Nextera XT Index Kit (Illumina inc).

Quantity and quality check of library on Agilent 4200 Tape Station

The amplified libraries were analyzed in 4200 Tape Station system (Agilent Technologies) using D1000 Screen tape as per manufacturer instructions. The mean of the library fragment size distributions are 594bp and 592bp for sample 1A and Sample 2A respectively. The libraries were sequenced on MiSeq using 2 \times 300 bp chemistry

Cluster generation and Sequencing

The gene-specific sequences used in this protocol target the 16S V3 and V4 region. They are selected from the Klindworth *et al.* (2013) publication. Evaluation of general 16S ribosomal RNA gene PCR primers for classical and next-generation sequencing-based diversity studies. *Nucleic Acids Res* 41(1) as the most promising bacterial primer pair.

This method can also be utilized to target other regions on the genome (either for 16S with other sets of primer pairs, or non-16S regions throughout the genome; i.e. any amplicon). The overhang adapter sequence must be added to the locus-specific primer for the region to be targeted (Figure 1). The Illumina overhang adapter sequences to be added to locus-specific sequences are:

Forward overhang: 5' TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAG-[locus-specific sequence]

Reverse overhang: 5' GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAG-[locus-specific sequence]

The Illumina Gene sequencing protocol can be used to sequence alternative regions of the 16S rRNA gene and for other targeted amplicon sequences of interest. When using this protocol for amplicon sequencing other than 16S rRNA, we can use instead the Generate FASTQ Workflow (secondary analysis option).

After obtaining the peak size from Tape Station profile, libraries were loaded onto MiSeq at appropriate concentration (10-20pM) for cluster generation and sequencing. Paired-End sequencing allows the template fragments to be sequenced in both the forward and reverse direction on MiSeq. The kit reagents were used in binding of samples to complementary adapter oligos on paired-end flow cell. The adapters were designed to allow selective cleavage of the forward strands after re-synthesis of the reverse strand during sequencing. The copied reverse strand was then used to sequence from the opposite end of the fragment.

QIIME is compressive software comprising of tool and algorithms such as FastTree for heuristic based maximum-likelihood phylogeny inference, the RDP classifier for the assignment of taxonomic data using a naive Bayesian classifier (Wang *et al.*, 2007) and others. This allow QIMME, which continues to undergo development, to easily and relatively adapt novel stand alone tools, and thus

improve in step with advances in the field of microbial community ecology.

To process the data of two samples, the following steps were performed:

- Sitching the PE data into single end reads.
- Picking Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs) based on sequence similarity within the reads, and picks a representative sequence from each OTU.
- Assigning the OUT to a taxonomic identity using reference databases.
- Calculated diversity metrics for each samples and compare the types of communities, using the taxonomic assignments.

OUT-picking identifies highly similar sequences across the sample and provides a platform for comparisons of community structure. All the sequence from the sample will be clustered into Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs) based on the sequence similarity. OTUs are clusters of sequences frequently intended to represent some degree of taxonomic relatedness done uclust at 97% sequence similarity and each resulting cluster typically represents a species. Since each OUT may be made up of many

sequences, a representative sequence for OUT is picked for downstream analysis. This representative sequence will be used for taxonomic identification of the OUT. This is done by setting assignment methods to the RDP classification system and a confidence of 0.8.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Tape-Station Profile of library for samples 1A and 2A

Tape station profile is prepared by Agilent Tape Station using D1000 Screen Tape for library profile base pair quantification. Figure-1 showed the base pair read for sample 1A and sample 2A.

Total bases read

The total base read for both the sample with reading 594bp for sample 1A (a) was showed in figure 1 and the base pair read for sample 2A (b) was 592bp for bacterial diversity.

Table 1 showed the total read and total bases for sample 1A and 2A after sequencing for bacterial diversity present in both the samples. In sample 1A the total read is 676,774 and total bases is 346,507,919 and in sample 2A the total read is 762,725 and total bases read is 391,653,372.

Figure 1: Library Profile of sample a) 1A and b) 2A on Agilent Tape Station using D1000 Screen Tape.

Table 1: Table showing the total bases read in both the samples.

S. No.	Sample	Reads	Total Bases	Data in MB
1	1A	676,774	346,507,919	~346
2	2A	762,725	391,653,372	~391

The present study was undertaken to extract the DNA from both the earthworm samples *Pheretima posthuma* and *Eisenia fetida*. The samples were named as 1A and 2A for the entire studies. The DNA was extracted from both the earthworm samples using c-TAB and Phenol : Chloroform Extraction method followed by AMPure XP bead purification and the total bacterial diversity was quantified. The protocol described by Illumina Gene sequencing protocol for 16S Metagenomic Sequencing Library Preparation is followed in this study.

The total base reads of bacterial diversity for both the samples 1A and 2A is 346,507,919 and 391,653,372 respectively which is very promising compared to other sequencing tools. Several DNA extraction procedures were suggested as CTAB method (cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide) Murray and Thompson 1980, Solid phase extraction methods e.g., Promega's DNA IQ (Eminovic *et al.*, 2005, DNA IQ manual), Applied Biosystems' PrepFiler (Brevnov *et al.*, 2009, PrepFiler manual), and Qiagen's QIAamp kits (Castella *et al.*, 2006, Greenspoon *et al.*, 1998): simple extraction process in which the DNA binds to paramagnetic or silica beads.

CONCLUSION

DNA was extracted by following c-TAB and Phenol: Chloroform Extraction method showed a very good result in this present study undertaken. Bacterial diversity count by following Illumina Gene sequencing protocol method of gene sequencing was very high compared to other protocol. This method can be suggested for further work in other group of microbes, pathogens and also animals for sequencing of bacterial DNA.

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